

Geospatial Artificial Intelligence for Solid Waste Recognition from UAV Imagery

Luca Morandini^{1*}, Alessio Buda¹, and Piero Fraternali¹

¹Politecnico di Milano, Department of Electronics, Information, and Bioengineering, via Ponzio 34/5, Milan 20133, Italy

Abstract. Illegal waste disposal has direct consequences on people's quality of life in affected areas. Exposure to hazardous waste substances has been linked to increased rates of multiple forms of cancer. Traditional inspection methods require time and manpower. Advances in UAV technology, combined with AI-enabled Computer Vision, offer a promising solution to significantly reduce survey time and the required workforce. The main contributions of this work are the evaluation of two Object Detection models, YOLOv8 and Faster R-CNN, trained to identify 7 waste materials from UAV imagery and the presentation of a practical pipeline to implement the proposed model in environmental agency workflows. To the best of our knowledge, no existing dataset or model has been designed to detect such a diverse range of waste types from UAV images. Results suggest that Object Detection is highly effective for regularly shaped waste categories such as *Textile*, *Pallets* and *Tires*, with the best YOLOv8 model achieving AP scores of 80.22%, 69.24% and 62.47% respectively. However, for waste materials with irregular boundaries, such as *Rubble* or *Mixed Items*, detection remains challenging. These findings provide valuable insights for future research in AI-driven environmental crime detection.

1 Introduction

Environmental crime is the third most prevalent form of criminal activity on a global scale, with an estimated annual growth rate of 5% to 7% and an estimated \$110–281 billion of generated losses every year. Illegal waste disposal, a significant form of environmental crime, has severe consequences for ecosystems, increase in pollution levels, reduction of biodiversity, and risks to human health. Furthermore, when buried or accumulated in piles, waste can produce leachate that percolates the terrain, with a detrimental impact on soil quality and groundwater.

Recent advances in Geospatial Artificial Intelligence (GeoAI), Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) and Computer Vision (CV) techniques have the potential to support environmental agencies in the investigation of waste disposal sites by increasing the efficiency of their territory monitoring activities, automating the identification of waste materials in suspicious areas and the assessment of the risk level of dumping sites.

The objective of this work is to investigate the strengths and limits of Deep Learning (DL) models, specifically Object Detection (OD) networks, in detecting and classifying waste materials on orthomosaics generated from UAV images portraying an inspected site.

* Corresponding author: luca.morandini@polimi.it

Two widespread OD models, YOLOv8 and Faster R-CNN, are optimized and compared and a practical pipeline is presented for integrating the proposed GeoAI-based waste detector into the investigation processes of law enforcement and environment protection agencies.

Experimental results prove that OD models are effective in recognizing regularly shaped waste categories, such as *Tires* and *Pallets*, with YOLOv8 achieving AP scores above 60% for certain materials. However, detection remains challenging for waste types with irregular shapes and textures, such as *Rubble* or *Mixed Items*.

2 Related Work

2.1 Literature Review

Different applications of DL approaches for waste detection in Remote Sensing (RS) data have been proposed [1, 2, 3]. Waste detection from UAV images encompasses a wide range of tasks, from urban litter monitoring to the detection of large illegal waste dumps. Some works concentrate on the identification of generic waste, some emphasize a specific category while others address the identification of multiple materials.

The employed DL task depends on the nature of the targeted waste materials. OD is used mainly for detecting single instances of waste, such as plastic bottles or metallic cans, whereas Semantic Segmentation (SS) is commonly employed when large piles of materials, such as construction debris, need to be recognized.

To detect plastic waste in water environments, OD models in the YOLO family are typically employed [4, 5]. Pre-trained deep learning YOLO models are proven to transfer well to plastic detection in terms of precision and speed of training [5]. Alternatively to DL approaches, a Random Forest Classifier to perform pixel-wise classification of multispectral images of marine scenarios is proposed [6]. Detection of litter in urban environments is also commonly treated as an OD task using YOLO [7] and Faster R-CNN [8] models because the targeted waste comprises individual objects with regular shapes. Differently, for the detection of solid waste over large regions, SS models are commonly employed [9, 10]. This approach enables the recognition of waste piles with irregular shapes (construction waste) or diverse patterns (household waste).

2.2 Available Datasets

Several works in the literature do not disclose the data used to train the models, thus hindering the reproducibility of results. Only five datasets for UAV waste detection are publicly available. They focus on the detection of a single type of waste, such as plastic bottles in land scenarios [11] (e.g. bush forest, flat land, grass) or generic plastic garbage in fluvial environments [4]. The dataset presented in [7] portrays waste in different contexts (e.g., street, urban, grassland) but considers only a generic *Rubbish* category. The dataset presented in [10] comprises three general waste categories (construction, household, mixed) and does not enable the detection of a wider range of more specific materials. Moreover, the waste types that can be recognized are limited by the low resolution of the images (3.8 cm/px GSD) which prevents the characterization of smaller objects with fine-grained textures.

3 Dataset

The dataset used for training and evaluating the proposed OD models has been created by performing several drone surveys and annotating the collected images with seven waste

categories. In this Section, the procedure for collecting and preparing drone images is illustrated along with a brief description of the annotated data.

3.1 Data Collection

The dataset comprises images acquired in 17 drone surveys on landfills and industrial waste disposal sites in Italy and Greece. The flights cover diverse environments: some areas exhibit minimal vegetation while other regions contain trees and shrubs. Some sites are categorized as industrial, whereas others are situated in rural settings. Drones used during acquisition were equipped only with an RGB camera and the collected images were combined using photogrammetry techniques to generate a georeferenced orthomosaic covering the inspected site. This approach standardizes the image resolution, which is set to 2 cm/px Ground Sample Distance (GSD), and the viewing direction, which is nadiral.

3.2 Dataset Preparation

Using a sliding window, 4,993 tiles have been extracted from the orthomosaic representations of the 17 flights. The resulting dataset spans seven waste categories and includes 3,346 bounding box annotations. This ensures that images with a standardised size of 640x640 px are obtained and the small overlap between adjacent tiles prevents some waste instances from being missed. The considered waste categories include *Metal Barrels*, *Mixed Items*, *Pallets*, *Plastic Packaging*, *Rubble*, *Textile*, and *Tires*. The *Textile* category includes bags of textile material. *Plastic Packaging* encompasses plastic bags of different colors and sizes, as well as plastic sheets typically used for packing or covering other materials. *Rubble* comprises piles of various fine-grained materials such as soil or dirt. *Mixed Items* consist of piles of hard to distinguish mingled materials. Such categories cover a diverse spectrum of targets, including waste for which it is possible to distinguish individual instances (e.g., *Metal Barrels* or *Pallets*) and waste occurring in piles with irregular boundaries (e.g., *Rubble*).

Some relevant features of the dataset need to be acknowledged. Firstly, 4,244 out of 4,993 images do not contain any waste item. This is due to the inherent nature of the investigated locations in which the waste piles are distributed sparsely over large areas. Moreover, some categories present high intra-class variability because their instances have very different colors, textures and shapes. This is especially true for the samples of *Rubble*, *Mixed Items* and *Plastic Packaging*. Nonetheless, such categories have been considered to validate the behavior of OD models for types of waste that frequently occur in dumping sites and are difficult to identify with an OD approach.

4 Methodology

4.1 Pipeline Overview

Environmental and law enforcement agencies are the main end-users interested in optimizing the analysis of the large number of waste disposal sites that must be monitored. The support provided by GeoAI tools, such as the pipeline proposed in this work, help to accelerate the inspection of suspicious illegal waste sites and to quickly assess their environmental impact. The proposed approach aims to compile a report about the identified materials automatically, to assess the extent of the waste present in the inspected site and to estimate the risk level. Using the proposed pipeline (Figure 1), after a site inspection, investigators download the collected UAV images and start the site analysis procedure. Firstly, a photogrammetry tool generates the orthomosaic of the surveyed site by combining all the aerial images. After this

step, smaller tiles are extracted from the orthomosaic which are processed by the OD model to identify and categorize any waste instance. Since the generated orthomosaic is georeferenced, all the detections can be geolocalized on a world map. This step is essential to enable investigators to visualize the detected waste, overlaid on the site orthomosaic, using any Geographic Information System (GIS) software they already use. Each waste instance is associated with a score denoting the confidence with which the OD model assigned the waste category, the estimated area in meters and the European Waste Code (EWC) that uniquely identifies the waste type. The EWC is a standardized ontology of waste materials defined by the European Commission, which is internationally recognized by all environmental and law enforcement agencies in Europe. Each EWC code is associated with a risk level indicating the environmental threat caused by the waste material.

Fig. 1. The proposed GeoAI-based waste detection pipeline.

4.2 GSD and Context Size

The main factors that characterize the inputs of the OD models are the GSD and the context size, i.e., the extent of the geographical area covered by each image. The GSD and the context size are related. Together, they define the tile size measured in pixels, which is a factor that affects the detection performance. Most popular OD models operate on square images of 512 px, 640 px or 800 px, which sets a boundary on the maximum tile size. The tile size selected for the experiments reported in this work is 640 px. The GSD has been selected based on a trade-off between spatial resolution and computational requirements. High spatial resolution is needed to identify fine-grained patterns and textures of certain materials (e.g. *Plastic Packaging*, *Pallets*) avoiding confusion with similar objects not classified as waste. On the other hand, high resolutions (lower GSD values) significantly increase the computation time and storage requirements for the site orthomosaic, especially for surveys covering large areas. The GSD selected for the experiments is 2 cm/px. Consequently, each tile extracted from the orthomosaic covers an area of 12.8 m. This context size enables the detection of smaller objects, such as *Metal Barrels* or *Pallets*, while also covering larger piles of *Rubble* or of *Mixed Items*.

4.3 Object Detection Architectures

The experiments compare two of the most popular OD models: YOLOv8 [12] and Faster R-CNN [13] which have different architectures and address the OD task with different approaches.

YOLOv8 tackles the OD task as a single regression problem by predicting all the objects in the image in a single stage. The backbone extracts relevant image features that are then fed to a series of fully connected layers (neck). For each object, the detection head predicts a confidence score, the bounding box coordinates, and the object class. This architecture results in a fast and efficient network able to locate objects without the need for a region proposal stage. The original network was pre-trained on COCO [14], a large dataset of natural images, therefore a two-stage training strategy is adopted to adapt the model to the new task. In the initial transfer learning stage, the knowledge learned by the model during pre-training (backbone features) is used to train the detection head to recognize waste materials. In the second stage, the entire model is fine-tuned to optimize the learned representation to the specific textures of waste materials.

Faster R-CNN is a two-stage OD network that applies a region-based approach. First, a Region Proposal Network (RPN) identifies coarse regions from the feature map extracted by the network backbone. Each Region of Interest (RoI) potentially containing an object is passed to the RoI pooling layer that extracts a feature vector from the feature map. Each region is individually processed by the detection head, which assigns an object class and refines the coarse bounding box predicted by the RPN. The original Faster R-CNN has been adapted by replacing the original feature extractor, responsible for generating a high-level representation of the input image, with a deeper ResNet-50 [15] backbone. Following the backbone, a Feature Pyramid Network (FPN) module has been introduced that combines features from different layers of the backbone, enhancing the model ability to detect objects at various scales. Despite the standard GSD, scale invariance is relevant for dealing with waste objects with very different sizes ranging from small *Metal Barrels* to large piles of *Rubble*. Also in this case, the original model pre-trained on COCO [14] must be adapted to the new task. A four-stage training strategy is adopted to first optimize the RPN and then the classification head. In the first stage, the RPN is trained to identify waste objects, while backbone and detection head are kept frozen. In the second stage, only the detection head is trained to discriminate waste materials in the proposed regions. In the last two stages, the backbone features are optimized first in combination with the RPN and finally with the detection head.

4.4 Experimental Setup

The 17 surveys are very diverse, covering different geographic contexts and sites, with a heterogeneous distribution of materials and a strong dissimilarity between waste instances. To overcome the high contextual shift between sites and provide a more robust estimate of model performance, a k -fold cross-validation strategy has been implemented for model evaluation. This procedure was also used to select the best configuration of YOLOv8 and Faster R-CNN and to tune their hyper-parameters, mainly the model variants. K -fold cross-validation is a popular technique used to assess the performance and generalizability of a DL model. The dataset is divided into k folds; the model is trained on $k-1$ folds and tested on the remaining fold. This process is repeated k times, with each fold used exactly once as the test set. In this work, each of the 17 sites is treated as a fold. At each iteration, one site is selected as a test set and the OD models are trained on the remaining sites. After each training, predictions are generated for the tiles in the test set. Finally, predictions for all 17 sites are combined and the performance is evaluated against the overall ground truth including all sites.

To avoid overfitting of the models on the training set, early technique is applied: the performance is monitored on the validation set and when it starts to deteriorate the training process is stopped. The validation set for each training fold is defined by randomly sampling images using a stratified strategy to maintain similar category distributions between the training and the validation sets.

5 Experiments

5.1 Evaluation Procedure

Using the k-fold cross-validation technique, a global validation set without duplicates cannot be defined since at each fold the validation set is extracted randomly. The absence of a global validation set prevents a thorough hyper-parameter tuning step and thus the definition of a confidence threshold. Consequently, only threshold-independent metrics are reported, namely per-class APs and mAP.

5.2 Results and Discussion

Different configurations of the models have been evaluated and extensive ablation studies have been performed. However, for brevity, in this paper only the best results for each model architecture are reported. The authors of the YOLOv8 model proposed 5 variants (nano, small, medium, large, extra-large) with increasing size and complexity. Among such variants, YOLOv8 medium obtained the best performance for waste detection. Due to the relatively small dataset, larger variants tend to learn features specific to the instances in the training set resulting in worse generalization capability on new scenarios. Results of YOLOv8 are presented in Table 1. The model struggles to detect categories commonly appearing in piles with various dimensions and irregular boundaries, such as *Rubble* or *Mixed Items*, but achieves promising results for categories of waste that typically appear as single or multiple instances with well-defined boundaries, such as *Pallets*, *Textile*, *Tires* or *Metal Barrels*.

In the experiments with Faster R-CNN, two variants of the ResNet backbone have been tested: ResNet-50 and ResNet-101. The latter is a larger version of the same network architecture with a much higher number of trainable parameters. Also in this case, the smaller variant, ResNet-50, obtained better performance, which can be justified as for the YOLO model. The best Faster R-CNN model achieves slightly worse results compared to the best YOLOv8 model (Table 1). Performance on *Pallets*, *Textile*, and *Tires* is promising, with AP@50 values close to or higher than 60%.

As the YOLO model, Faster R-CNN obtains poor results on categories appearing as piles, such as *Rubble* and *Mixed Items*, suggesting that approaching the detection of these materials as an OD task is not suitable. For such heterogeneous materials, a segmentation approach may be better suited because the DL model learns to predict a category for each pixel in the image rather than isolating entire objects. Moreover, *Rubble* is very challenging to be identified from a nadiral viewpoint since, without elevation cues, it can be easily confused with rough terrain or dirt land with very similar visual appearance. Compared to the best YOLO model, Faster R-CNN performs significantly worse on *Metal Barrels* (26.34% AP@50). This might be due to the distribution of *Metal Barrels* annotations across different sites: 62% of the samples in this class appear in a single site, thus the performance of the model is highly dependent on how well it predicts instances in such a location. The RPN of the Faster R-CNN failed to learn features of *Metal Barrels* that are generalizable on other sites, differently from the YOLOv8 model which obtained good performance on this class (58.26% AP@50). Finally, when considering the *Plastic Packaging* class, Faster R-CNN

outperforms YOLOv8. The ability of Faster R-CNN to focus on RoIs helps the model detect small plastic bags that YOLOv8 cannot identify.

Table 1. Performance comparison between YOLOv8 and Faster R-CNN. YOLOv8 outperforms Faster R-CNN on all waste categories, except for *Plastic Packaging*.

Metric	Category	YOLOv8	Faster R-CNN
AP@50	Pallets	69.24%	63.03%
	Textile	80.22%	74.00%
	Tires	62.47%	57.21%
	Plastic Packaging	6.00%	12.33%
	Metal Barrels	58.26%	26.34%
	Rubble	4.68%	3.57%
Mixed Items	22.93%	22.68%	
mAP@50		43.40%	37.02%

Figure 2 presents some True Positive detections of the best YOLOv8 model. A detection is considered True Positive when it has a high overlap with the corresponding ground truth annotation and the predicted category matches the true category.

Fig. 2. True Positive examples, red: model predictions, blue: ground truth annotations. Categories (from the top left corner): *Tires*, *Textile*, *Pallets*, *Mixed Items*.

Figure 3 shows examples of False Positive predictions. This demonstrates that the model has learned features characterizing waste categories but then fails when similar features appear in non-waste objects.

Fig. 3. False Positive examples, red: model predictions.

Categories: *Pallets*, *Mixed Items*, *Rubble*. A metal sheet with a corrugated pattern is mistaken for an instance of *Pallets*, a tree crown for *Mixed Items* and a rough terrain patch for *Rubble*.

Finally, Figure 4 presents examples of False Negative detections, i.e., waste not detected. For the *Plastic Packaging* category, the model struggles with smaller annotations. In the *Metal Barrels* category, it fails to detect instances that differ from most annotations in the training set with different colors and orientations. For *Rubble*, the model is unable to predict most large patches that cover the entire tile.

Fig. 4. False Negative examples, blue: ground truth annotations.

Categories: *Plastic Packaging*, *Metal Barrels*, *Rubble*.

6 Conclusions

In this paper, we have presented a dataset comprising optical UAV images acquired in 17 survey flights performed in Italy and Greece. The images portray 7 classes of waste materials with very different visual appearance: *Metal Barrels*, *Mixed Items*, *Pallets*, *Plastic Packaging*, *Rubble*, *Textile*, and *Tires*. The data set has been used in a waste detection experiment, in which we have compared the performance of two popular OD architectures (YOLOv8 and Faster R-CNN). The results prove that the OD approach is effective ($AP > 60\%$) for waste items with a regular shape but fails to detect waste dumps with blurred boundaries and irregular form. The waste detector is the basis of a practical GeoAI-based pipeline that supports the investigation procedure of law enforcement and environment monitoring agencies.

Future research directions include the expansion of the dataset with additional sites and waste categories, and the exploration of segmentation models to address irregularly shaped waste piles. Moreover, self-supervised learning techniques will be adopted to pre-train

detection models on non-annotated sites to learn meaningful features from unlabeled data by creating supervisory signals (labels) from the data itself. This approach improves generalization ability and reduces the need for human annotation. Finally, multispectral and multimodal data (images + point clouds) can be exploited to improve performance on irregular materials, where information from RGB cameras is insufficient to discriminate waste instances from the background.

This research was funded by European Union's Horizon Europe project PERIVALLON - Protecting the European territory from organised environmental crime through intelligent threat detection tools, under grant agreement no. 101073952.

This work was supported by the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports of the Czech Republic through the e-INFRA CZ (ID: 90254).

References

1. P. Fraternali, L. Morandini, S. L. H. González, "Solid waste detection, monitoring and mapping in remote sensing images: A survey", *Waste Management*, vol. **189**, no. 12, pp. 88-102 (2024)
2. L. Zhou, X. Rao, Y. Li, X. Zuo, Y. Liu, Y. Lin, Y. Yang, "SWDet: Anchor-Based Object Detector for Solid Waste Detection in Aerial Images", *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Applied Earth Observations and Remote Sensing*, vol. **16**, pp. 306-320 (2023)
3. R. N. Torres, P. Fraternali, "Learning to Identify Illegal Landfills through Scene Classification in Aerial Images", *Remote Sensing*, vol. **13**, p. 4520 (2021)
4. W. Luo, W. Han, P. Fu, H. Wang, Y. Zhao, K. Liu, Y. Liu, Z. Zhao, M. Zhu, R. Xu, G. Wei, "A Water Surface Contaminants Monitoring Method Based on Airborne Depth Reasoning", *Processes*, vol. **10**, no. 1, p. 131 (2022)
5. N. Maharjan, H. Miyazaki, B. M. Pati, M. N. Dailey, S. Shrestha, T. Nakamura, "Detection of River Plastic Using UAV Sensor Data and Deep Learning", *Remote Sensing*, vol. **14**, no. 13, p. 3049 (2022)
6. I. Cortesi, A. Masiero, G. Tucci, K. Topouzelis, "UAV-based river plastic detection with a multispectral camera", *The International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences*, vol. **43**, pp. 855-861 (2022)
7. M. Kraft, M. Piechocki, B. Ptak, K. Walas, "Autonomous, Onboard Vision-Based Trash and Litter Detection in Low Altitude Aerial Images Collected by an Unmanned Aerial Vehicle", *Remote Sensing*, vol. **13**, no. 5, p. 965 (2021)
8. T. Malche, P. Maheshwary, P. K. Tiwari, A. H. Alkhayyat, A. Bansal, R. Kumar, "Efficient solid waste inspection through drone-based aerial imagery and TinyML vision model", *Transactions on Emerging Telecommunications Technologies*, vol. **35**, no. 4 (2024)
9. S. Gao, Y. Liu, S. Cao, Q. Chen, M. Du, D. Zhang, J. Jia, W. Zou, "IUNet-IF: identification of construction waste using unmanned aerial vehicle remote sensing and multi-layer deep learning methods", *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, vol. **43**, pp. 7181-7212 (2022)
10. Y. Liu, B. Zhao, X. Zhang, W. Nie, P. Gou, J. Liao, K. Wang, "A Practical Deep Learning Architecture for Large-Area Solid Wastes Monitoring Based on UAV Imagery", *Applied Sciences*, vol. **14**, no. 5, p. 2084 (2024)

11. J. Wang, W. Guo, T. Pan, H. Yu, L. Duan, W. Yang, “Bottle detection in the wild using low-altitude unmanned aerial vehicles”, 21st International Conference on Information Fusion (FUSION), pp. 439-444 (2018)
12. M. Yaseen, “What is YOLOv8: An In-Depth Exploration of the Internal Features of the Next-Generation Object Detector,” arXiv (2024)
13. S. Ren, K. He, R. Girshick, J. Sun, “Faster R-CNN: Towards Real-Time Object Detection with Region Proposal Networks”, IEEE transactions on pattern analysis and machine intelligence, vol. **39**, no. 6, pp. 1137-1149 (2016)
14. T.-Y. Lin, M. Maire, S. Belongie, J. Hays, P. Perona, D. Ramanan, P. Dollár, L. Zitnick, “Microsoft coco: Common objects in context”, Computer Vision - ECCV 2014: 13th European Conference, Zurich (2014)
15. K. He, X. Zhang, S. Ren, J. Sun, “Deep residual learning for image recognition”, IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition, Las Vegas (2016)